

PECULIARITIES OF PERFORMANCE OF UZBEK FOLK INSTRUMENTS.

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When we look at the history of music, we see that the Uzbek people have always been interested in art and the study of art. In particular, they studied the composition and performance of musical instruments. These are also reflected in the music literature. “As a result of archeological expeditions organized in the 30s and 40s of the century (led by S.L. Tolstov, V.A. Vyatkin, M.B. Masson and others), valuable information was obtained in the study of Central Asian culture, including folk instruments. Found cultural monuments; a flute, a rubab-shaped instrument, a drum resembling a modern circle, and drummers playing similar instruments. These are the masterpieces of spool pots found in cities such as Afrosiob, Toprakkala, Aytaram (called Aytaram Frieze). They are described as practicing a variety of musical instruments: the junta, the tanbur, the rubobs, the oud, the shemane (musician), the chagana, the chiltor, the nay, the burgu sunray, the karnay, and the doira. Folk instruments have become an integral part of human life, incorporating them into the life and work of the people of Central Asia.” [1]

Uzbek folk instruments are diverse and differ in their performance capabilities, functions and structure.

The group of stringed instruments, consisting of tirnama, nokhunli, stringed percussion, and bows, is very rich and includes dutar, dombra, tanbur, afghan rubobi, kashkar rubobi, chang, gijjak, and sato.

instruments include nay, karnay, koshnay, bulamon, and sunray.

Examples of percussion are drums and drums.

In developing performance skills, students should first be introduced to these instruments and taught to play the instrument perfectly, taking into account which instrument they have a strong desire to play.

The dutar has a soft sound, the noxious skull is carved or ribbed, the relatively long and thin handle attached to it is attached to the skull with a thin lid, and the long handle is attached to the double handle or two strands of silk thread. there is. Typically, the curtains are 13 and form a completely non-chromatic sound string with a range of more than two octaves. Dutor's two silk strings are tuned to a quartet, quintet, or unison (octave). The main method of execution in Dutar is scratching. At the same time, the richness of the dutars, the use of the right hand and fingers are developing. Dutor's works are characterized by a double texture.

The Afghan rubabi (also known as the Bukhara rubabi) has a unique shape and is a percussion instrument. The top is covered with leather, and a thin cover is glued to the top of the narrowed sides of the large and deep carving. Normally, only 4 curtains are attached to the bowel on a thick handle that is aligned with the bowl part, and the rest are glued to the wooden lid with chopsticks. The rubab usually has 5 main strings (including unison adjustable 1-2,3-4 twin strings) and 10-11 resonant strings attached to the side ear (earphones). when the burning strings are tuned to the interlocking quartet, the resonant forms a similar step-by-step ascending second. Although the range is in the range of two octaves, Afghan rubab is used almost exclusively by professional folk musicians, soloists and ensembles, mainly in Bukhara, Uzbekistan.

The upper part of the Kashgar rubobi semicircular carved skull is covered with leather, and two wooden branches protruding from the sides of its thick and long-handled mounting part stand out as a characteristic feature of this instrument. . The number of Kashgar rubobi threads is 5: three are made of silk (or stakes), two are made of wire (now all of them are made of wire of different thickness). They are set to quartet, quintet. The rubab handle is connected to a 19-23 thin strand that forms a series of chromatic sounds of three octaves (now almost all of

them have metal sticks attached to the top). The rubab is performed with a simple mediator (nohunak) like an Afghan rubab.

Dust is a stringed percussion instrument with a thin wooden cover (deca) glued to a trapezoidal piece of wood. Its 40 strings are pulled over the lid. They are based on 14 strings, one of which is a thick bottom string, and the remaining 13 strings are three each. These strings are further divided into two groups. The first group leans on the donkey on the right and makes one sound because it is not divided into two, and the second group makes two sounds because it is split over the middle donkey. In general, they form a diatonic sound within two octaves. The dust is beaten with two wooden sticks.

Gijjak - a round carcass, usually carved from apricot stalks, is covered with leather, and the long handle has no curtains. The bow is a straight or slightly bent bowstring, to which the horse's bridle is attached by means of certain fasteners. There are 3 or 4 strings in a string. There are also six- to seven-stringed, or more precisely three-stringed, two-stringed worm species. The first specimens were two-stranded. The nets are adjusted to the quarter. Currently, the most widely used four-string adjustable quartet quartet. The range is close to three octaves.

The group of Uzbek folk instruments is very wide. Reed, bone, and wooden tools are important. For example:

Nay is common among many peoples of the East, and is made of reeds, wood, and metal, and has a variety of varieties accordingly. It is usually 450 to 520 mm long and has a blower and six drill holes on the front side of a slender tube of equal diameter, which is held horizontally like a flute. The range is two and a half octaves. The sound is a strong squeak and a flat one.

Made of neighboring reeds. It combines the same tubes and has the same acoustic properties. Neighbor's tubes, which are tuned to the unison and are identical in appearance, are usually tied with a thin thread and tied to the thread only during the playing. Each reed has seven finger holes.

Percussion instruments are one of the most popular musical instruments in the Orient. They play an important role in the musical practice of the Uzbek

people. The percussion instruments, which play a very important role in the life of music in our country, are drums and drums.

In the practice of music, the function of each instrument and its ensembles is also different. For example, he used stringed instruments, mainly in "camera" conditions.

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